

DEVELOPING UNIVERSAL COMPETENCES EXPLANATION OF ADAPTIVE SKILLS IN SOFT SKILLS

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Abstract: Universal competencies are currently defined as SOFT SKILLS, i.e. having life and adaptability skills. It is highlighted that if life and adaptability skills are considered as important and basic knowledge and skills, they will enable a person to work successfully in his/her chosen professional activity.

Key words: basic knowledge, continuous education, unclear goals, confusing plans, well-tested path, time management, self-management, communication, modern technologies.

The policy of the state of Uzbekistan in the field of education is closely related to the implementation of the concept of development of the higher education system until 2030[1] in all types of continuous education. The relevance of this concept is explained by the fact that with the rapid growth of the digital economy, the need for personnel to constantly work on themselves and the need for not only personnel with a narrow set of specialized skills, but also specialists with a wide range of universal competencies.

Universal competences are currently defined as SOFT SKILLS, i.e. acquiring vital and adaptive skills. When life and adaptability skills are considered as important and foundational knowledge and skills, it can be clearly seen that they enable a person to succeed in his chosen career.

Also, the scientific works devoted to the formation of these skills will further enrich the local scientific and popular scientific publications. As a result of a random search of scientific articles of 2009-2019 on this topic, more than 46 scientific works of authors dealing with the formation of life skills were identified. The idea of these articles is united within the framework of the principle of continuous education. As the main component of the national model of personnel training, continuous education is the basis of qualified competitive personnel training and includes all types of education, state educational standards, the structure of the personnel training system and its operating environment. In turn, the goal of the "National Personnel Training Program" is to fundamentally reform the education sector, to free it from the ideological views and prejudices of the past, to create a national system of highly qualified personnel training that meets high moral and ethical requirements at the level of developed democratic countries.[2]

This proves that the above-mentioned Concept is a logical continuation of this program in its modern interpretation. For example, among the tasks of the program, the system and content of personnel training is aimed at restructuring based on the prospects of social and economic development of the country, the needs of society, and the modern achievements of science, culture, technique and technology. However, there is a gap between the current traditional educational system, i.e., the educational programs used in the continuing education system, educational processes, and the requirements claimed by "future competencies" [3]. This, in turn, increases the relevance of applying SOFT SKILLS to the continuous education system.

When a person determines the direction of work on himself, he seeks to know the actions that lead to progress in the direction of choice. What prevents a person from developing:

1. Unclear goals, confused plans, lack of understanding in which direction to take actions and why it should be done;
2. Unwillingness to radically change something in one's work and personal life;
3. Fear of starting a new job that no one has done yet. Preferring to follow the "beaten path".
4. Reluctance to take time to reflect on one's actions and results;
5. Non-interest of the second party. Competencies specific to Soft Skills.

As mentioned above, Soft Skills do not have a clear classification, but experts study them by dividing them into four leading areas:

1. Basic communication skills. They allow the development of mutual relations, form the ability to conduct a conversation, help to act adequately in tense situations.

2. Self-management skills. They help a person to be able to control his behavior and situation, to use time rationally.

3. Productive thinking. It is represented by the ability to control one's thoughts, to be able to adapt properly, to be able to direct.

4. Management skills. It is necessary for everyone who takes on a leadership position at some point. There are soft-skills that match each direction. Communicative skills include the ability to listen, persuade and argue, build and maintain relationships, negotiate, and make social presentations. Self-management means the ability to manage oneself, control stress situations, monitor personal improvement, know time management, [4] show initiative, be persistent, and approach work with enthusiasm.

Recommendations on how to develop soft skills help everyone to actively move forward. It is necessary to take into account the following general rules:

1. Development should be made a continuous process. In turn, it is necessary to have experience, to be able to solve complex tasks, to act better than in a simple way. The main thing is not to stop.
2. Learning to plan the stages of development competently;
3. Use of different forms;
4. To show curiosity, to study the happenings around.
5. It is very important to choose areas of work that will be of real importance.
6. Forming the habit of reading more is an excellent solution.

To sum up, the planned start of each work helps to timely eliminate the negative consequences of this work, and most importantly, the successful completion of the work. In turn, an individual plan for the formation of soft-skills can be developed at any convenient time. It is important that a person consciously takes responsibility for his personal development.

References:

1. On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. October 8, 2019, No. PF-5847.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. About the national personnel training program // Barkamol avlod - the foundation of Uzbekistan's development. - Tashkent: Sharq, 1997. - B. 31-61.
3. Fedorova O.V. Formirovanie kompetentsiy ekrektnoy deyatel'nosti v sootvetstviy s professionalnymi standartami u studentov fakultate informatsionnykh tekhnologii vuza // International electronic magazine "Educational technology and society (Educational Technology & Society)" - 2016. - V.19. - No. 1. - S.476-484. - ISSN 1436-4522.
4. Measuring soft skills & life skills in international youth development programs. - URL: <https://www.fhi360.org/sites/default/files/media/documents/resource-yp-measuring-soft-skills.pdf> (data obrashcheniya: 09.10.2019).
5. Tatyana V. Vorobyova, Larisa G. Poleshchuk. Ethnic tolerance among students. WELLSO 2015 - II International Scientific Symposium on Lifelong Wellbeing in the World. 2016 Published by Future Academy www.FutureAcademy.org.uk. -R. 304.

